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Influence of school environment and academic achievement of higher secondary commerce students

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Abstract

This study was conducted on the school environment and academic achievement of higher secondary commerce students in Cuddalore district, Tamilnadu. The random sampling technique with the normative survey method was used to collect 200 samples from the area of the study. For the data collection, the investigator used the school environment and academic achievement scale. The data collected were analyzed using frequency counts, percentages, mean and standard deviation to answer research questions, while t-test and coefficient of correlation of fit was deployed to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. The results showed that 1. There is no significant difference between male and female higher secondary commerce students in their School Environment. 2. There is no significant difference between rural and urban higher secondary commerce students in their School Environment. 3. There is significant difference between male and female higher secondary commerce students studying in their academic achievement. 4. There is significant difference between rural and urban area higher secondary commerce students in their academic achievement. 5. There is significant relationship between the school environment and academic achievement of higher secondary commerce students.

Keywords: School environment; Academic Achievement; Higher Secondary Commerce Students

1. Introduction

The school environment represents the facilities and disciplinary policies and practices of various things, just as an environment of safety, support, respect and challenges for higher secondary school students across different domains of social, physical, emotional and cognitive. A school is set for the effective teaching and learning process. The physical environment of the school is conducive to learning, developing healthy communication and interaction for promoting a sense of belonging and self-esteem and promoting learning and self-fulfilment. Dave (1963), "School environment is the conditions, process and psychological stimuli which affect the educational achievement of the child". The school environment consists of physical facilities- infrastructure, labs, libraries, classrooms, TLM, playgrounds for the welfare of the social as well as psychological behaviour of students, teachers as well as administrators. The students who undergo school studies have special needs for academic excellence, most of the students input into our higher institutions for their further studies, most of them later come with academic excellence. They found ways to have academic success to defend after graduation.

1.1. Need for the study

In this increasing competitive world, every school student needs a high level of achievement of their performance on the part of their marks awarded. The entire system of education is focused on the academic achievement of students.

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When a proper and pleasant school environment is provided for school students, good learning takes place effectively and efficiently. The education of a school student and their achievement is determined by the diverse and dynamic performance of teachers and the facilities provided by them for the school students. Since the school environment influences the academic achievement of the students, the researcher has undertaken the problem of the school environment and the academic achievement of higher secondary commerce students.

1.2. Statement of the problem

The study has been entitled “Influence of School Environment and Academic Achievement of Higher Secondary Commerce Students”

1.3. Operational definition

1.3.1. School Environment

School Environment refers to the psycho-social climate of the school as perceived by the students in school. It includes six dimensions: Creative stimulation, cognitive encouragement, permissiveness, acceptance, rejection, and control.

1.3.2. Achievement

Academic achievement is a measure of knowledge gained in formal education, usually indicated by test scores, grades, points, average and degrees. (Encyclopedia Dictionary of Psychology and Education, 2005).

Higher Secondary Students: By higher secondary students, the Investigator means the students doing standards XI and XII in higher secondary schools under the Tamil Nadu state board syllabus.

Objectives

- To find out the level of school environment among higher secondary commerce Students.
- To find out the level of school environment among higher secondary commerce Students with respect to gender
- To find out if there is any significant difference between male and female higher secondary commerce students in their school environment.
- To find out if there is any significant difference between Rural and Urban higher secondary commerce students in their school environment.
- To find out the level of academic achievement among higher secondary commerce Students.
- To find out the level of academic achievement among higher secondary commerce Students with respect to gender.
- To find out if there is any significant difference between male and female higher secondary commerce students in their academic achievement.
- To find out if there is any significant difference between Rural and Urban higher secondary commerce students in their academic achievement
- To find out if there is any relationship between school environment and academic achievement among higher secondary commerce students.

1.4. Hypotheses of the study

- There is no any significant difference between Male and Female Higher secondary commerce students in their school environment.
- There is no any significant difference between Rural and Urban Higher secondary commerce students in their school environment.
- There is no any significant difference between Male and Female, higher secondary commerce students in their academic achievement.
- There is no significant difference between Rural and Urban higher secondary commerce students in their academic achievement.
- There is no significant relationship exists between school environment and academic achievement among higher secondary commerce students.

2. Methodology and sample used

For the present study, the investigator has selected the normative survey method. It is the most popular method, which attempts to describe and interpret conditions, practices, processes, trends, effects, attitudes, beliefs and so on. In the

present study, the population is the higher secondary school students in Cuddalore District. For the present study, 200 higher secondary School students were taken as the sample. The sample was collected using a random sampling technique.

2.1. Tools used in the study

- School Environment scale, prepared and developed by the Investigator.
- Academic achievement

2.2. School environment

The School Environment Scale consisted of 55 statements, teacher behaviour 12, classroom climate 9, control and safety 11, acceptance and rejection 12, and facilities 11, related to 5 dimensions. These items related to each variable were given separately, but the variables were not mentioned in the scale.

2.3. Academic achievement

For achievement, the investigator took the half-yearly marks in respective schools obtained by the higher secondary commerce students in XIth and XIIth standard.

2.3.1. Validity

The investigator established content validity for the present research tool. The tool is given to experts. These experts constructively criticised and gave valuable suggestions. The words of some of the statements were changed and modified and irrelevant statements were removed. Only the items which truly checked and retained. Thus, the content validity of the tool was established.

2.3.2. Reliability

Internal consistency of the instrument was found by the split-half Method. The reliability coefficient by Spearman Brown formula was 0.89, which is significant at 0.01 level of significance. However, Sample Reliability was established by the investigator using the test re-test method. The School Environment Scale is administered to 100 students twice after a gap of 15 days. The Correlation Coefficient ‘r’ become the two tests are found to be 0.81. Hence, the tool is highly reliable.

2.3.3. Statistical techniques used

The investigator for analysing the data uses the following major statistical techniques. Percentage analysis, Mean, Standard deviation and Test of significance (t-test) and correlation analysis

3. Analysis of the data - objectives testing

Table 1 Level of School Environment among Higher Secondary Commerce Students

Variables	Low		Average		High	
	No	%	No	%	No	%
School Environment	38	19	123	61.5	39	19.5

It is inferred from the above table that 19% of the students have low, 61.5% of them have moderate and 19.5% of them have high level of School Environment.

Table 2 Level of School Environment among Higher Secondary Commerce Students with respect to Gender

Variable	Categories	Number	High		Average		Low	
			Count	%	Count	%	Count	%
Gender	Male	96	21	21.9	56	58.3	19	19.8
	Female	104	25	24	58	55.8	21	20.2

The table revealed that out of 96 male higher secondary commerce students 19.8%, 58.3% and 21.9 low, moderate and high level of School Environment respectively. Out of 104 female higher secondary commerce students 20.2%, 55.8% and 24% low, moderate and high level of School Environment respectively.

Null Hypothesis: 1, There is no significant difference between Male and Female Higher secondary commerce students in their school environment.

Table 3 Significant difference between Male and Female Higher secondary commerce students in their school environment

Variable	Category	N	Mean	SD	Calculated t - Value	Table Value	Remarks at 5% level
Gender	Male	96	56.04	7.63	1.39	1.96	NS
	Female	104	57.43	6.55			

Since the calculated t- value (1.39) is less than the table value (1.96) at 5% level of significance, the null hypothesis is accepted. Hence, it is concluded that there is no significant difference between male and female higher secondary commerce students in their School Environment.

Null Hypothesis: 2, There is no significant difference between Rural and Urban Higher Secondary Commerce Students in their school environment.

Table 4 Significant difference between Rural and Urban Higher Secondary Commerce Students in their School Environment

Variable	Category	N	Mean	SD	Calculated t - Value	Table Value	Remarks at 5% level
Locality	Rural	108	58.38	7.58	1.30	1.96	NS
	Urban	92	57.08	6.63			

Since the calculated t- value (1.30) is less than the table value (1.96) at 5% level of significance, the null hypothesis is accepted. Hence, it is concluded that there is no significant difference between rural and urban higher Secondary Commerce Students in their School Environment.

Table 5 Level of Academic Achievement among Higher Secondary Commerce Students

Variable	Low		Average		High	
	No	%	No	%	No	%
Academic Achievement	24	12	150	75	26	13

It is inferred from the above table that 12% of the male students have low, 75% of them have moderate and 13% of them have high level of Academic achievement.

Table 6 Level of academic achievement among Higher Secondary Commerce Students with respect to Gender

Variables	Low		Average		High	
	No	%	No	%	No	%
Male	20	20.8	59	61.5	17	17.7
Female	23	22.1	60	57.7	21	20.2

The table revealed that out of 96 male higher secondary commerce students 20.8%, 61.5% and 17.7% had low, moderate and high level of academic achievement respectively. Out of 104 female higher secondary commerce students, 22.1%, 57.7% and 20.2% had low, moderate and high level of academic achievement respectively.

Null Hypothesis: 3, There is no significant difference between Male and Female Higher secondary Commerce students in their academic achievement

Table 7 Difference between Male and Female of higher secondary commerce students in their academic achievement

Variables	Mean	SD	Count N	Calculated value 't'	Remarks
Male	126.18	27.05	108	3.30	S
Female	132.05	26.82	92		

Since the calculated t- value (3.30) is higher than the table value (1.96) at 5% level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence it is concluded that there is significant difference between male and female higher secondary commerce students in their academic achievement.

Null Hypothesis: 4, There is no significant difference between Rural and Urban, of higher secondary commerce students in their academic achievement

Table 8 Difference between Rural and Urban, of higher secondary commerce students in their academic achievement

Variables	Mean	SD	Count N	Calculated value 't'	Remarks
Rural	126.86	26.32	108	2.39	S
Urban	131.15	27.53	92		

Since the calculated t- value (2.39) is higher than the table value (1.96) at 5% level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, it is concluded that there is significant difference between rural and urban higher secondary commerce students in their academic achievement.

Null Hypothesis - 5, There is no significant relationship exists between School Environment and academic achievement among higher secondary commerce students.

Table 9 Significant Relationship exists between School Environment and Academic Achievement among Higher Secondary Commerce Students.

Variable	N	Calculated r- value	Table value	Remarks
School Environment and Academic Achievement	200	0.63	0.17	S

Since the calculated r-value is greater than the table value at 5% level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, it is concluded that there is a relationship between school environment and academic achievement among higher secondary commerce students.

4. Findings

- 19.0% students have low, 61.5% students have moderate and 19.5% of them have a higher level of school environment respectively.
- Male higher secondary school student 19.8%, 58.3% and 21.9% low, moderate and high level of School Environment respectively. Female higher secondary commerce students 20.2%, 55.8% and 24% low, moderate and high level of School Environment respectively.
- There is no significant difference between male and female higher secondary commerce students in the school environment.
- There is no significant difference between rural and urban higher secondary commerce students in their School Environment.

- There is significant difference between rural and urban higher secondary commerce students in their School Environment.
- There is significant difference between rural and urban higher secondary commerce students.
- There is significant relationship between school environment and academic achievement among higher secondary commerce students.

5. Discussion on the results

There is significant difference between male and female higher secondary commerce students of their academic achievement compared with the mean score girls are better than boys. This may be due to the fact that girls are far more systematic. Female students have a higher level of achievement in commerce than male students. Male students may have a lot of our world distractions like outing, chatting, and mass media like TV, movies and the internet. Normally, female students remain at home most of the time after school is over and they put serious efforts into their studies. The result shows that there is significant difference between rural and urban school students in their academic achievement compared with the mean score of urban students being better than that of rural students. This may be the reason why all the learning facilities are available in urban areas. But there is significant relationship between school environment and academic achievement with reference to background variables. It shows that these variables do have an impact on the establishment of relationships between those traits.

Recommendations and educational implications of the study

- The government should provide funds for schools in an adequate manner to buy the aids, and the regular staff should be appointed for teaching commerce in all schools.
- Teacher's behaviour must be conducive and clear cut friendly manner for the students.
- Guidance and counselling may be given to the students about various good study habits and their importance in their academic career at the higher secondary level.
- The mode of examinations to test the aural, oral and communicative skills of students, is just being introduced by the Directorate of Government Examinations with due credit at the final and concluding examination at the higher secondary stage, thereby enabling them to develop good achievement.
- A "How to study" summer course of 30-45 days may be imparted to the interested students and those who have undergone this course may be given due preference in joining the desired group at the high secondary stage itself.
- Group discussions may be arranged by the teachers then and there to enable them to be active.
- The low achievers may be induced to participate in co-curricular activities of their interest in the view of helping them develop good academic achievement.
- The various elements that are acting as hurdles or barriers in developing good study habits may be identified and not allowed to exert their impact in this regard.
- The students themselves may be made to realize the importance of good study habits in their academic career.
- The students should plan a proper time schedule. The time schedule may be followed strictly, which will help the students to become routine in their minds of the students. While preparing a time schedule by the students, priority may be given according to the needs of the programme.
- Spaced studying can be encouraged instead of un-spaced studying. This may improve one's memory power and help in avoiding studying and help in avoiding daydreaming due to continuous studying.

Suggestions for further research

- This study covers only the Cuddalore district in Tamil Nadu state. A similar study may also be conducted in other districts of Tamil Nadu.
- A comparative study on the academic achievement of school students could be undertaken.
- Academic achievement in relation to psychological aspects of the subjects could be studied.
- A similar study may be undertaken in other subjects such as Mathematics, Physics, Chemistry, Social Science and languages.
- A study of academic achievement in relation to intelligence and other social variables may be taken up.
- A comparative study on the academic achievement of professional and other college students may be done.
- The investigator had made the study of only the students of XI and XII standard, the study can be extended to different classes of all types of schools, including ICSE CBSE and Anglo Indian schools at different levels, such as higher secondary, arts and science and professional college.

- A similar study can be undertaken with different categories of students physically and mentally challenged and the impact of the problems they face in life and their effect on their academic achievement.

6. Conclusion

Ron Fry (2000) says, “The parent’s involvement is absolutely essential to a child’s eventual success. A parent, not even for a minute, can underestimate the importance of his/her commitment to his/her child’s success.’ Nancy L. Weishew (1993) points out; “parents can help to improve their children’s behavior in school by becoming more involved in their education, monitoring their actions, and helping to increase their achievement, educational expectations and positive self-perceptions’. It is clear that parents have a specific role in developing one’s achievement.

The teacher will change the way one studies. Effective teaching with its four components, knowledge, understanding, application and skill, can definitely elevate one’s own study habits. Some teachers encourage the students to memorize and some others emphasize the need for learning by understanding, avoiding memorization. Hence, in developing a study habit, it’s not only the student who performs, but also a teacher. Teachers are unique in their teaching approach. Accordingly, a student adopts a particular approach in a particular class. As is the teacher, so is the student.

Higher secondary education plays a very significant role in every individual life since after this education all decisions are made for the future. Students need proper guidance for the management of their time and efforts for better prospects.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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